

FAMILY SYNERGY AS A FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF "I-CONCEPT" IN ADOLESCENCE

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Abstract. This article examines the influence of family synergy on the formation of "I-concept" in adolescents. Family synergy is understood as the harmonious interaction of family members based on shared values, respect, emotional closeness, and moral responsibility. Particular attention is paid to the role of parents in the development of adolescents' self-perception, self-esteem, motivation level, and self-regulation ability. An empirical study conducted among parents of students in grades 8-9 revealed that positive acceptance, cooperation, and parental involvement in a teenager's life contribute to the formation of a mature and stable "I-concept". At the same time, a high level of authoritarianism and emotional rejection negatively affects the child's psychological state. The obtained results emphasize the need to create an atmosphere of mutual understanding, support, and cooperation in the family that contributes to the personal development of adolescents and the formation of their positive self-image.

Key words: family synergy, "I"-concept, adolescent, parental acceptance, cooperation, emotional closeness, self-esteem, psychological climate, authoritarianism, self-regulation.

OILAVIY SINERGIYA - O‘SMIRLIK DAVRIDA “MEN-KONSEPSIYASI”
RIVOJLANISHINING OMILI SIFATIDA

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada oilaviy sinergiyaning o‘smirlarda "Men-konsepsiyasi" shakllanishiga ta’siri ko‘rib chiqiladi. Oilaviy sinergiya deganda, oila a’zolarining umumiy qadriyatlar, hurmat, hissiy yaqinlik va axloqiy mas’uliyat asosida o‘zaro kelishilgan munosabatlari tushuniladi. O‘smirning o‘zini o‘zi anglashi, o‘zini o‘zi baholashi, motivatsiya darajasi va o‘zini o‘zi boshqarish qobiliyatini rivojlantirishda ota-onaning rolga alohida e’tibor qaratiladi. 8-9-sinf o‘quvchilarining ota-onalari o‘rtasida o‘tkazilgan empirik tadqiqot shuni ko‘rsatdiki, ijobiy qabul qilish, hamkorlik va ota-onalarning o‘smir hayotida ishtirok etishi yetuk va barqaror "Men-konsepsiyasi"ni shakllantirishga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, avtoritarlik va hissiy rad etishning yuqori darajasi bolaning psixologik holatiga salbiy ta’sir ko‘rsatadi. Olingan natijalar oilada o‘zaro tushunish, qo‘llab-quvvatlash va hamkorlik muhitini yaratish zarurligini ta’kidlaydi, bu esa o‘smirning shaxsiy rivojlanishiga va unda ijobiy o‘zlik qiyofasini shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Kalit so‘zlar: oilaviy sinergiya, Men-konsepsiyasi, o‘smir, ota-ona munosabati, kooperatsiya, hissiy yaqinlik, o‘zini-o‘zi baholash, psixologik muhit, avtoritarizm, o‘zini-o‘zi boshqarish.

СЕМЕЙНАЯ СИНЕРГИЯ КАК ФАКТОР РАЗВИТИЯ “Я-КОНЦЕПЦИИ” В
ПОДРОСТКОВОМ ВОЗРАСТЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается влияние семейной синергии на формирование «Я-концепции» у подростков. Под семейной синергией понимается согласованное взаимодействие членов семьи, основанное на общих ценностях, уважении, эмоциональной близости и моральной ответственности. Особое внимание уделяется роли родителей в развитии самосознания подростка, его самооценки, уровня мотивации и способности к саморегуляции. Эмпирическое исследование, проведённое среди родителей учащихся 8–9 классов, выявило, что положительное принятие, кооперация и участие

родителей в жизни подростка способствуют формированию зрелой и устойчивой «Я-концепции». В то же время высокий уровень авторитарности и эмоционального отвержения негативно сказывается на психологическом состоянии ребёнка. Полученные результаты подчеркивают необходимость создания в семье атмосферы взаимопонимания, поддержки и сотрудничества, которая способствует личностному развитию подростка и формированию у него позитивного образа себя.

Ключевые слова: семейная синергия, Я-концепция, подросток, родительское принятие, кооперация, эмоциональная близость, самооценка, психологический климат, авторитаризм, саморегуляция.

Introduction.

Family relations, especially the relationship between parents and children, have been one of the key issues since the first days of society's existence. With the development of society, the significance of this aspect only increases. This is explained by the fact that it is precisely in the system of parent-child relationships that the achievements of humanity as a link between social institutions are most fully assimilated, and traditions are passed down from generation to generation as a spiritual heritage. Thus, the future of any society, people, and nation largely depends on the state of family relations. For this, a healthy and spiritually strong family atmosphere is necessary. Synergy plays an important role in achieving such an atmosphere [1,45-46].

Synergy implies that as a result of the interaction of individual parts, something new arises - an additional quality or structure. In the context of a family, such a quality is the nature and depth of the relationship between its members. Synergy is born in the interaction between husband and wife, between parents and children. It is in such interactions that creative ideas are formed, new opportunities and alternative solutions emerge.

This additional part can be figuratively represented as "third person". When a sense of "we" arises between two people, they become not just two, but as if three - the very connection between them acquires a separate, independent meaning. This also applies to the relationship between parents and children. Such a "third party" arising on the basis of interaction is family culture, which is formed on the basis of a common goal and a system of values based on principles.

Problem statement.

Synergy is not just mutual openness, but the formation of shared values, goals, and a responsible approach to adherence to them. It forms a moral law within family culture, encouraging honesty, openness, and courage in resolving complex issues rather than avoiding them or avoiding communication.

This "third person" becomes a kind of supreme moral authority, the embodiment of the collective conscience, common goals, and traditions of the family. It restrains family members from immoral acts, abuse of power or authority. As long as the family lives according to this inner authority, its members realize that position, power, money, and status are not property, but a trusted management intended to serve others. But when a person breaks the agreement with this moral center and becomes a "law for itself", the connection breaks down. People become distant, focusing on themselves and their interests, and the feeling of commonality disappears. As a result, family culture transforms from a culture of interdependence into a culture of independence, and the miracle of synergy disappears.

Solution method.

Our research is based on the scientific hypothesis that the psychological environment in the family and interpersonal relationships, parents' attitude towards the child, that is, the level of their acceptance and healthy psychological cooperation, can influence the formation of "I-concept" in

adolescents. The study involved parents of students in grades 8-9 of general education schools. A total of 80 respondents were surveyed.

It is well known that the personality of parents has an important influence on the formation of a person's self-awareness. That is why the main tool in this case is the test questionnaire developed by A.Ya.Varga and V.V.Stolin. This questionnaire is a psychodiagnostic method designed to determine parents' attitudes towards their children.

As is known from the laws of age psychology, parents' attitude towards a child manifests itself in the first months of early childhood, and sometimes even in infancy. According to the concept of "animation complex", the first signs of socialization in a child appear already at 1.5 months of age - this is the manifestation of a smile on the face and the corresponding expression of positive emotions in the voice. However, the object of our research requires analysis of situations occurring at a higher level of social influence, aimed at studying the impact of family relations on the social perception of adolescents.

Parents attitude towards children is understood as a system of various feelings and behavioral manifestations of adults towards children. From a psychological perspective, it is a pedagogical social attitude that includes rational, emotional, and behavioral components. These components are assessed using a special questionnaire, which forms the basis of this methodology. The use of certain terms by R.S. Nemov led to some changes in the processing and interpretation of the obtained results. The methodology consists of 61 questions distributed across 5 scales reflecting parents' attitudes towards their children:

1. "Acceptance - Rejection". Reflects an emotional positive (acceptance) or negative (rejection) attitude towards the child.
2. "Cooperation". Evaluates parents desire to interact with the child, interest in their activities, and participation in them.
3. "Symbiosis" - Reflects interpersonal distance in communication with the child. The parent feels one with the child, strives to satisfy all their needs, to protect them from life's difficulties. The parent experiences anxiety when the child begins to strive for independence, as they themselves are not ready to give them autonomy.
4. "Authoritarian hypersocialization" - Reflects the form and degree of control over the child's behavior. Shows whether relationships are built in a democratic or authoritarian style.
5. "Little loser" - reflects the peculiarities of the child's perception and understanding by the parent. This last scale shows how adults react to the strengths and weaknesses of a child's abilities, their successes and failures.

Results and examples. The results of the method are presented below:

Fig. 1. Results of the diagnostic method for assessing parental attitudes towards children
(n=80)

Note: I - "Acceptance - Rejection"; II - "Cooperation"; III - "Symbiosis"; IV - "Authoritarian hypersocialization"; V - "Little loser".

It was established that all groups of subjects on the "acceptance - rejection" scale showed high scores. This indicates a clearly expressed positive attitude towards the child. An adult accepts a child as they are, recognizes and respects their individuality, supports their interests, dedicates a lot of time to them, and doesn't regret it. At an average level, parents demonstrate a desire to be with their children - this is more a desire than a practical necessity. Low scores mean that parents don't understand children well, are offended by them, and are unable to provide them with practical support.

High results on the "cooperation" scale show that adults show keen interest in the child's interests, value their abilities, encourage initiative and independence, and are concerned about their successes. Parents are interested in the child's activities, the realization of their plans and dreams, rejoice in their achievements, and strive to develop their intellectual and creative abilities. However, some parents limit themselves to only dreams, lacking a clear plan of action.

Parents of 8th-grade students showed high scores on the "symbiosis" scale. This indicates that they do not establish psychological distance between themselves and the child, but try to be as close as possible, to satisfy their basic needs, and to protect them from possible difficulties. While the parents of 9th-grade students showed low scores, this indicates a sharp psychological distance and a low level of care. Such parents cannot act as good educators.

According to the "authoritarian hypersocialization" scale, high indicators are observed in all groups. This means that adults demand unquestioning obedience from children, do not consider their opinions, and authoritarian control prevails. Strict rules are established, discussions are excluded, and the child is given minimal independence.

Analyzing the results of the "little loser" scale, it can be said that parents perceive their child as a failure. For them, his passions, thoughts, and feelings seem insignificant. This attitude is reflected in the adolescent's psychological state: self-esteem decreases, a system of self-regulation is not formed, motivation for cognition decreases, responsibility is avoided. Emotional contact between parents and children is a necessary condition for a child's mental well-being. If parents cannot manage their emotions and understand their children's feelings, then no matter how hard they try, they will not achieve results. Children especially need effective emotional contact with their parents. The relationship between parents and children directly affects their emotional development.

Conclusion.

According to the results of our research, excessive emotional distance manifests itself in the following ways: adults expect only socially acceptable behavior from children, complete obedience, and unquestioning obedience to instructions. A child's disobedience and insistence on their position causes irritation and excessive strictness in adults.

Thus, we can conclude that a person's self-awareness largely depends on the psychological climate in the family and the personal example of the parents. The formation of "I-concept" in adolescents is connected with their position in the parental system and the nature of family relationships. Parental role and status directly influence the maturity of a teenager's personality.

Considering that the disruption of the psychological climate in the family shapes negative behavioral traits in the child, parents are advised to strive to create an atmosphere of cooperation within the family.

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